

Ambient Air Quality and the Incidence of Selected Diseases: Some Urban Health Observations in Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract

The quality of air is determined by the extent of atmospheric pollution. The USEPA identifies six criteria pollutants namely particulate matter (PM), ground level ozone, carbon monoxide, sulphur oxides, nitrogen oxides and lead exposure as toxic and injurious to human health. Thus, there is a need to examine ambient air quality and incidence of selected diseases in Lagos, Nigeria. The data for the study include a five-year sampling on criteria pollutants and data on selected airborne diseases that were collected for the same period of time. Data analysis adopted the use of multiple regression for examining the relationship between ambient criteria pollutants and the occurrence of diseases. GIS procedure was also employed to produce a map showing the spatial pattern of criteria pollutants. The findings reveal an R^2 of 19.8, 13.9, 8.9, 8.4 and 16.8 percent respectively for asthma, bronchitis, heart failure, lung cancer and tuberculosis. The results show a low level of association and this was attributed to other causal factors responsible for the occurrence of the selected diseases. However, this study provides evidence of an association between outdoor air pollution and increased risk from these diseases. Therefore, the study recommends that governments, and other stakeholders in health sectors should harmonize efforts, resources and ideas towards effective planning, monitoring, policy implementation and provision of facilities that could control and ameliorate the presence of pollutants to which urban residents are exposed thereby reducing the health effects from such exposures.

Keywords: airborne diseases, air pollution, criteria pollutants, ambient air

Introduction and Statement of the Problem

Studies have shown that over half of the global population lives in urbanized areas (United Nations, 2012) with a consequent urbanization and intense human activities occasioned by resource consumption. There is also an increase in chemical emissions and waste disposal resulting in a variety of environmental problems, including the potentially toxic criteria pollutants (Charlesworth *et al.*, 2010). Urban air quality in many large cities are adversely affected by air pollution such as particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) and other criteria air pollutants (Laro & Raheem, 2017).

The United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2012) classified air pollutants into two groups: criteria and hazardous air pollutants (HAPs). The criteria pollutants are pollutants that can have an adverse effect on health and the environment. They include particulate matter, oxides of nitrogen, oxides of sulphur, carbon (II) oxide and lead. Emission of air pollutants are caused by different anthropogenic activities which can be categorized into their source groups: motor traffic, industry, power plants and domestic fuel (Lirong *et al.*, 2004; Olukayode, 2005; Mathuros *et al.*, 2006).

Air quality can be a critical reflection of the ambient atmospheric pollution, relative to the potential to inflict harm on the environments (WHO, 2002). Air is said to be polluted when there is 'the presence in the outdoor atmosphere of one or more contaminants such as dust, fumes, gas, mist, odour, smoke, or vapour in such concentration and duration as to make them actually or potentially injurious to human, plant or animal life, or property or which interferes with the comfortable enjoyment of life and property' (World Bank, 1978). Human health is threatened with diseases and early mortality as a consequent of pollution particularly in emerging economies facing rapid industrialization and urbanization. By reducing air pollution levels, countries can reduce the burden of disease from stroke, heart disease, lung cancer, and both chronic and acute respiratory diseases, including asthma (WHO, 2014). Moreover, reduction in outdoor air pollution also reduces emissions of CO₂ and short-lived climate pollutants such as black carbon particles and methane, thus contributing to the near and long-term mitigation of climate change (WHO, 2014).

Ground level ozone (O₃), oxides of nitrogen (including NO, NO₂, and NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), and sulphur dioxide (SO₂) are not only pollutants themselves but also react with many other compounds such as volatile organic compounds (VOCs) leading to changes in atmospheric composition (Atkinson, 2000). Researches have shown that air pollution leads to detrimental impact on the environment such as haze, smog and acid rain particularly in urban

and industrialized cities with high vehicular traffic. Epidemiological studies have also shown that PM₁₀ is associated with morbidity and mortality rates particularly due to cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses (Peters *et al.*, 2001; Nigel *et al.*, 2002; Pope *et al.*, 2002; Lirong *et al.*, 2004). Exposure to carbon monoxide can result in fatigue, headaches, dizziness, loss of consciousness and even death. Nitrogen oxides and sulphur dioxide have been shown to have association with immune system impairment, exacerbation of asthma and chronic respiratory diseases, reduced lung function and cardiovascular disease (Osuntogun & Koku, 2007; Hopkins *et al.*, 2009).

Lagos, the commercial hub of Nigeria, has over 60% of industry concentration in Nigeria. These industries contribute significantly to air pollution because of the emission of smokes and gases of various magnitudes due to their diesel-powered engines. In this way, industrial sites are always polluted above the accepted level. Akinola *et al.* (2014) posited that the increasing human activities, especially industrial and vehicular emissions are posing great environmental challenges that have resulted in loss of life and destruction of properties in the state. The overall effects of air pollution on Lagos residents and environments contribute to drag in the efforts for its most sustainable programs (Akinola *et al.*, 2014).

Study Area

Lagos state is located between latitudes 6°.35N to 6.58°N and longitudes 3°.45'E to 3.75°E of the Greenwich meridian in the south western part of Nigeria. The state has a tropical wet and dry climate with an all year-round precipitation in many parts of the state. Wet season is characterised by a double maximum of rainfall usually from March to July and the other in late August to early September. A dry spell may occur from late September to early November. The annual mean rainfall is between 1381.7mm and 2733.4mm in recent time from one location to another. The maximum temperature ranges between 29°C - 34°C, the lowest being in the

month of July and the highest in February and a minimum temperature varies between 24°C - 28°C. The relative humidity varies seasonally with an average of 70% throughout the year.

The vegetation of the study area is made up of two types namely; swamp forest of the coastal belt and dry lowland rain forest. The swamp forest is a combination of mangrove forest and coastal vegetation developed under the brackish conditions of the coastal areas, swamp fresh water lagoons and estuaries. Lying to the north of the swamp forest is the lowland (tropical) rain forest zone which stretches from Ikeja through Ikorodu. Economically valuable trees such as teak, tripochiton, seletrocylon (arere), banceleadiderrichil (opepe) and terminahia (idigbo) can be to be found in some parts of the study area. Lagos State occupies an area of 3,577 square kilometres, which represents 0.4% of Nigeria's landmass with a marine shoreline of about 180km extending inland to a maximum distance of about 32km. Lagos is the most populous city in Nigeria, the second fastest-growing city in Africa and the seventh in the world (www.lagosstate.gov.ng). The NPC (2016) estimated of the population of Lagos state at around 21 million, making Lagos the largest city in Africa.

The study area accounts for over 60% of the federation's total industrial investment and the largest concentrations of industries can be found in Ikeja, Alimosho and Kosofe local government areas (www.lagosstate.gov.ng). Other specific locations of numerous industries include Apapa, Surulere, Shomolu, Mushin, Oshodi-Isole, Agege, Amuwo Odofin, and Ikorodu among others. See fig. 1 for the map of the study area.

Figure 1. Lagos State showing sample areas

According to Brunekreef (2005), ambient particulate matter levels in cities of developing countries including Nigeria are generally much higher than in developed countries because of dispersed heating with small-scale solid fuel use, uncontrolled industrial emissions, and the large numbers of non-catalyst two-stroke engine vehicles. Ediagbonya et al. (2012) proposed that atmospheric environmental problems, had received scanty attention in Nigeria but were gradually becoming a subject of increasing national significance because air pollution is a major threat to human life. Most people inhale pollutants while at home or commuting to work irrespective of the mode of transportation (Ekpenyong et al., 2012). Depending on the dose and the exposure time, these pollutants have the potential to cause far-reaching adverse health effects in man, but principally affecting the respiratory and cardiovascular systems (Ekpenyong et al., 2012).

The World Health Organization (2002), reported that about 2.4 million people worldwide (including about 93,700 Nigerians) die each year from causes directly attributable to air

pollution. Akinola et al. (2014) indicated that studies have shown that in Lagos state vehicular emissions are the highest point source contributors to carbon emission into the environment, followed by the manufacturing industries. Unending traffic jams in Lagos metropolis also results in commuters spending several unproductive hours in traffic and increased avoidable emissions of CO₂ and other pollutants. A study conducted by the Lagos Metropolitan Transport Management Authority (LAMATA) on air quality between 2003 and 2007 indicated that vehicular emission contributes approximately 43% ambient air pollution in Lagos. The continuous expansion, population increase and transformation of the Lagos city have contributed to its present polluted states. However, assessment of the health effect of air pollution in developing countries is difficult because of lack of cohesive air quality policies in combination with poor environmental monitoring and a paucity of disease surveillance data (Briggs, 2003). Therefore, this study becomes imperative in examining the relationship between criteria air pollutants and incidence of some selected diseases. The aim of the study is to examine the ambient air quality and the incidence of selected diseases in Lagos. This is with a view to investigate the relationship that may exist between the spatial pattern in the exposure to ambient air quality and the incidence of selected diseases in Lagos, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Data required and sources

The sources of data for this study are both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources include the coordinates of the sample sites. The secondary data includes five years data of criteria pollutants, the pollutants are Particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), Ground level (O₃) Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), and carbon dioxide (CO) Guideline for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, NO₂, CO and Ground level O₃, were also obtained from the WHO publications, five years data on air pollution, maps, and statistical data obtained from published works.

Methods of data collection

Study sites were selected with a view to giving a holistic representation of air quality status of the area. The study area was categorised into three groups based on the predominant land use types. Thus, Lagos was divided into high traffic, industrial and residential areas. Areas considered as residential areas were land use in which housing predominates. In the light of the above, state government staff quarters and estates owned by private agencies were also considered. The high traffic areas are the major road intersections where high volumes of traffic are experienced during the peak hours of the day while areas with high concentration of industries were considered as industrial areas. It must be noted that this categorisation is not water tight as these characteristics may occur in all areas with varying intensities (See table 1)

Table 1: Showing Sites Distribution in the Study Area.

LANDUSE TYPE	LOCATIONS/SITES
RESIDENTIAL	Agege Housing Estate; Oko-oba Ikeja G.R.A: SoboArobiodu street. Magodo Estate: CMD Road, Shangisha Ogba Staff Quarters; Ogba Secretariat; Alausa: front of Skye bank Maryland Junction, Ikeja General Hospital: Frontage of LASUTH
HIGH TRAFFIC	Ojodu-Berger: Berger Roundabout Iyana-Ipaja: Under Bridge Oshodi B/Stop: Oshodi Specomil: Inside Ikeja Industrial Estate
INDUSTRIAL	Wemabod: Adjacent Guinness Nigeria PLC office Wempco: Industrial Estate Ogba Ize-Iyamu Matori

Source: Author's Fieldwork (2016)

Figure 2: Sampling Sites in the Study Area
 Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2016

Direct measurement of coordinates of the fifteen sample sites from the field with the aid of the global positioning system GPS.

The secondary data required for this study were sourced from the Lagos State Ministry for Environment and Ministry of Health, Lagos state.

Data on Criteria pollutants: The data on criteria pollutants were obtained from Ministry of Environment (2009-2013) Lagos State. The data are particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ground level ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide and carbon monoxide. This was required for the study because the atmospheric pollutants have the potentials for deterioration and damage to both public health and the environment. Data on air quality related diseases such as bronchitis, lung cancer, asthma and heart failure were source from Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Gbagada, Mushin, Isolo and Somolu General Hospital in the area of study from 2009-2013. This is with a view to give an accurate representation of the data. A map of the study area was obtained from Lagos state Ministry of Physical Planning and urban development.

Methods of data analysis

ArcGIS was employed to produce the map of the spatial distribution of criteria pollutants in Lagos area. To examine the relationship between the five criteria pollutants and the occurrence of five selected diseases in Lagos state, a multiple regression analysis was used. The regression model is denoted as:

$$Y = a + bx_1 + bx_2 + bx_3 + bx_4 \dots bx_n + e \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (1)}$$

Y = dependent variables; X = independent variables

a = the intercept constant; b = regression co-efficient; e = residual error term

Where, Y = Selected diseases

X₁- X₆= Criteria pollutants i.e. PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂, NO₂, CO and O₃

X₁ = PM_{2.5} (mg/m³)

X₂ = PM₁₀ (mg/m³)

X₃= SO₂ (ppm)

$$X_4 = \text{NO}_2 \text{ (ppm)}$$

$$X_5 = \text{CO (ppm)}$$

$$X_6 = \text{O}_3 \text{ (ppm)}$$

Note:

*This model was repeated for each of the diseases.

*Mean of selected diseases for the period of study was adopted as the measure of disease occurrence

*Mean of criteria pollutants for the period of study was adopted as the measure of pollutants

Results and Discussion

Criteria Pollutants and the Occurrence of Asthma

The dependent variable is reported cases of asthma while the independent variables are the six criteria pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃). Table 2 shows the results of the multiple regression analysis with an R² which signifies that the identified criteria pollutants accounted for 19.8% variability in the reported cases of asthma in the study area. This low percentage is expected because the criteria pollutants used in this study are not the only determinant of incidence of asthma, though they can precipitate the disease, but this is also a function of the level of exposure of the individual. Earlier, the Committee on the Medical Effects of Air Pollution (COMEAP) (1995) concluded that exposure to ambient concentrations of air pollutants is associated with an increase in exacerbations of asthma in susceptible populations such as children and the elderly. The question of whether air pollution causes asthma is still open for debate. However, there is evidence to suggest causation.

Table 2: Model Summary of Relationship between asthma and Criteria Pollutants

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.445 ^a	.198	-.011	1.00538504

a. Predictors: (Constant), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃

Source: Author’s Computation, 2016

Table 3 shows that for every 1% increase in PM₁₀, CO₂, SO₂, O₃, there is 1.34%, 0.094%, 2.218%, and 23.708% increase in the occurrence of asthma in the study area, respectively. This is represented in the expression below:

$$Asthma = -2.647 - 1.413_{PM2.5} + 1.337_{PM10} + .094_{CO} - 3.605_{NO_2} + 2.218_{SO_2} + 23.708_{O_3} \dots\dots\dots eq. 2$$

As shown above, ground level ozone gases are the most important criteria pollutants associated with asthma in the study area. The model summary (Table 2) for asthma and criteria pollutants indicates that about 20% of the variation observed in asthma occurrence could be attributed to the occurrence and variation in criteria pollutants in sampled sites.

Table 3: Relationship between Asthma and Criteria Pollutants

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Beta	Std. Error	
(Constant)	-2.647		1.581	-1.675 .108
PM2	-1.413		1.944	-.495 -.727 .475
PM10	1.337		1.110	.690 1.204 .241
CO	.094		.291	.221 .323 .749

No ₂	-3.605	2.325	-2.219	-1.550	.135
So ₂	2.218	1.993	1.648	1.113	.277
O ₃	23.708	12.563	.465	1.887	.072

a. Dependent Variable: (Asthma)

Source: Author's Computation, 2016

Also, as shown in Table 3, for every 1% decrease in PM_{2.5} and NO₂, there is -1.413% and -3.605% decrease in the occurrence of asthma in the study area, respectively. This result coincides with the findings of Koren (1995) that the concentration of ambient particulate matter with PM₁₀, primarily in combination with high sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and sulphate particulate matter has been associated with increased hospitalisation for asthma.

Criteria Pollutants and the Occurrence of Bronchitis

In this study, bronchitis is the dependent variable, while the independent variables are the six criteria pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃). Table 4 shows the results of the multiple regression analysis with an R² which signifies that the identified criteria pollutants accounted for 13.9% variability in the reported cases of bronchitis in the study area. This low percentage was due to the fact that the criteria pollutants used in this study were not the only determinant of incidence of bronchitis. The United States National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (2011) established that chronic bronchitis is caused by repeated irritation and damage of the lung and airway tissue, and smoking is the most common causes of chronic bronchitis, with other causes including long-term exposure to air pollution, dust and fumes from the environment, and repeated episodes of acute bronchitis. A substantial body of epidemiological research corroborates the assertion that outdoor air pollution, and in particular traffic-related air pollution, is a contributing factor to premature respiratory mortality and morbidity (Kunzli *et al.*, 2000).

Table 4: Model Summary of Relationship between Bronchitis and Criteria Pollutants

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.373 ^a	.139	-.085	1.04164544

a. Predictors: (Constant), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃

Source: Author’s Computation, 2016

Table 5 shows that for every 1% increase in PM₁₀, SO₂, O₃, there is 1.028%, 1.974%, and 9.619% increase in the occurrence of bronchitis in the study area, respectively. This is represented in the equation below:

$$Bronchitis = .085 - 2.299_{PM_{2.5}} + 1.028_{PM_{10}} - .018_{CO} - 2.352_{NO_2} + 1.974_{SO_2} + 9.619_{O_3} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. 3}$$

As indicated above, ground level ozone gases are the most important criteria pollutants associated with bronchitis in the study area. The model summary (Table 4) for bronchitis and criteria pollutants indicates that about 10% of the variation observed in bronchitis could be attributed to the occurrence of criteria pollutants in the area of study.

Table 5: Relationship between Bronchitis and Criteria Pollutants

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.085	1.638		.052	.959
PM _{2.5}	-2.299	2.014	-.805	-1.142	.265
PM ₁₀	1.028	1.150	.531	.893	.381
CO	-.018	.301	-.041	-.058	.954

NO ₂	-2.352	2.409	-1.447	-.976	.339
SO ₂	1.974	2.065	1.467	.956	.349
O ₃	9.619	13.016	.189	.739	.467

a. Dependent Variable: (Bronchitis)

Source: Author's Computation, 2016

Based on the results in Table 5, for every 1% decrease in PM_{2.5}, CO and NO₂, there is -2.299%, -0.018% and -2.352% decrease in the occurrence of bronchitis in the study area, respectively.

Relationship between Criteria Pollutants and the Occurrence of Heart Failure

The American Heart Association (2010) issued a scientific statement concluding that exposure to air pollution contributes to cardiovascular illness and mortality. It was elaborated that short-term exposure to air pollution can increase the risk of heart failure, heart attack, stroke and arrhythmias in susceptible people, such as the elderly or those with pre-existing medical conditions. In this study, heart failure is the dependent variable, while the independent variables are the criteria pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃). Table 6 show the results of the multiple regression analysis with an R² of 0.089, which signifies that the identified criteria pollutants accounted for 8.90% variability in the reported cases of heart failure in the study area. The reason for this low percentage can be attributed to the fact that criteria pollutants alone does not determine the incidence of heart failure, pre-existing medical conditions and susceptibility are also a major factor to be considered. These results corroborate the assertion posited by the American Heart Association.

Table 6: Model Summary of Relationship between Heart Failure and Criteria Pollutants

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
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1 .298^a .089 -149 1.07194240

a. Predictors: (Constant), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃

Source: Author's Computation, 2016

Table 7 shows that heart failure hospitalisation was associated with criteria pollutants. However, for every 1% increase in PM₁₀, CO, SO₂, O₃, there is 1.274%, 0.018%, 2.114%, and 10.607% increase in the occurrence of heart failure in the study area, respectively. Also, for every 1% decrease in PM_{2.5} and NO₂, there is -2.525%, and -2.469% decrease in the occurrence of heart failure in the study area, respectively.

Table 7: Relationship between Heart Failure and Criteria Pollutants

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized t		Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.208	1.685		-.123	.903
PM _{2.5}	-2.525	2.072	-.884	-1.218	.235
PM ₁₀	1.274	1.184	.658	1.076	.293
CO	.018	.310	.043	.058	.954
NO ₂	-2.469	2.479	-1.519	-.996	.330
SO ₂	2.114	2.125	1.570	.995	.330
O ₃	10.607	13.395	.208	.792	.437

a. Dependent Variable: (Heart Failure)

Source: Author's Computation, 2016

Based on the results in Table 7, the relationship between heart failure and criteria pollutants can be written as shown in equation 4.

$$HeartFailure = -208 - 2.525_{PM_{2.5}} + 1.274_{PM_{10}} + 0.018_{CO} - 2.469_{NO_2} + 2.114_{SO_2} + 10.607_{O_3} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. 4}$$

4.5.4 Relationship between Criteria Pollutants and the Occurrence of Lung Cancer

The International Agency for Research on Cancer (2013) classified ambient air pollution as a cancer-causing agent (Carcinogen, group 1). The IARC evaluation showed an increasing risk of lung cancer with increasing levels of exposure to outdoor air pollution and particulate matter. In this study, the dependent variable is lung cancer, while the independent variables are the criteria pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃). the results of the multiple regression analysis with an R² of 0.084 was shown in Table 8, this signifies that the identified criteria pollutants accounted for 8.40% variability in the reported cases of lung cancer in the study area. The reason for this low percentage is the fact that ambient air pollutants are not the leading cause of lung cancer rather it is smoking, also it is a function of the level of individual exposure to the criteria pollutants.

Table 8: Model Summary of Relationship between Lung Cancer and Criteria Pollutants

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.290 ^a	.084	-.155	1.07467988

a. Predictors: (Constant), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃

Source: Author’s Computation, 2016

As indicated in Table 9, for every 1% increase in PM₁₀, CO, SO₂, O₃, there is 1.048%, 0.177%, 1.343%, and 8.665% increase in the occurrence of lung cancer in the study area,

respectively. Also, for every 1% decrease in PM_{2.5} and NO₂, there is -2.638%, and -1.900% decrease in the occurrence of lung cancer in the study area, respectively.

Table 9: Relationship between Lung Cancer and Criteria Pollutants

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.150	1.690		.089	.930
PM _{2.5}	-2.638	2.078	-.924	-1.270	.217
PM ₁₀	1.048	1.187	.541	.883	.386
CO	.177	.311	.416	.570	.574
NO ₂	-1.900	2.486	-1.169	-.764	.452
SO ₂	1.343	2.130	.998	.630	.535
O ₃	8.665	13.429	.170	.645	.525

a. Dependent Variable: (Lung Cancer)

Source: Author’s Computation, 2016

Based on the results in Table 9, the relationship between lung cancer and criteria pollutants can be written as shown in equation 5.

$$LungCancer = .150 - 2.638_{PM_{2.5}} + 1.048_{PM_{10}} + .177_{CO} - 1.900_{NO_2} + 1.343_{SO_2} + 8.665_{O_3} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. 5}$$

Relationship between Criteria Pollutants and the Occurrence of Tuberculosis

Despite the established relationship between tobacco smoking, active and passive smoking, indoor air pollution and tuberculosis, the impact of outdoor air pollution on the development of tuberculosis has not been affirmed. In this study, analysis of criteria pollutants data and formally reported tuberculosis cases was carried out. Tuberculosis is the dependent variable,

while the independent variables are the six criteria pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃). As indicated in Table 10, the result of multiple regression analysis with an R² of 0.168 means that the identified criteria pollutants accounted for 16.80% variability in the reported cases of tuberculosis in the study area. The reason for the low percentage was attributed to the fact that ambient air pollutants alone does not determine the incidence of tuberculosis.

Table 10: Model Summary of Relationship between Tuberculosis and Criteria Pollutants

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.410 ^a	.168	-.049	1.02408237

a. Predictors: (Constant), PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃

Source: Author's Computation, 2016

Table 11 shows that for every 1% increase in PM₁₀, CO, SO₂, O₃, there is 1.332%, 0.026%, 2.392%, and 18.860% increase in the occurrence of tuberculosis in the study area, respectively. PM_{2.5} and NO₂ concentrations were not associated with the incidence of tuberculosis. However, for every 1% decrease in PM_{2.5} and NO₂, there is -1.621%, and -3.581% decrease in the occurrence of tuberculosis in the study area, respectively.

Table 11: Relationship between Tuberculosis and Criteria Pollutants

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-1.762	1.610		-1.094	.285
PM2	-1.621	1.980	-.567	-.819	.421

PM10	1.332	1.131	.688	1.178	.251
Co	.026	.296	.062	.089	.930
No ₂	-3.581	2.369	-2.204	-1.512	.144
So ₂	2.397	2.030	1.781	1.181	.250
O ₃	18.860	12.796	.370	1.474	.154

a. Dependent Variable: (Tuberculosis)

Source: Author’s Computation, 2016

However, this study provides evidence of an association between outdoor air pollution and an increased risk of tuberculosis (TB). Hwang et al. (2014) achieved similar results in his study of ‘‘Impact of outdoor air pollution on the incidence of tuberculosis in the Seoul metropolitan area, South Korea’’. Based on the results in Table 11, the relationship between tuberculosis and criteria pollutants can be written as shown in equation 6.

$$Tuberculosis = -1.762 - 1.621_{PM_{2.5}} + 1.332_{PM_{10}} + 0.026_{CO} - 3.581_{NO_2} + 2.397_{SO_2} + 18.860_{O_3} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq.6}$$

Some urban health observations and concluding remarks

From the findings, it was observed that there are spatial variations in the distribution of criteria pollutants in the Lagos area. Within the residential areas, Ikeja GRA and Magodo have the highest concentration of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀SO₂ and NO₂. In high traffic areas, Ojodu-Berger and Iyana-Ipaja have the highest concentration of criteria pollutants while Ize-Iyamu, Matori and Specomil in industrial areas have the highest level of criteria pollutants. Among the three landuse types, the high traffic has the highest concentration of pollutants (see figure 3). However, long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} is associated with an increase in the long-term risk of cardiopulmonary mortality by 6–13% per 10 µg/m³ of PM_{2.5} (Pope *et al.*, 2002). Susceptible groups with pre-existing lung or heart disease, as well as elderly people and children, are particularly vulnerable. For example, exposure to PM affects lung development in children,

including reversible deficits in lung function as well as chronically reduced lung growth rate and a deficit in long-term lung function (WHO, 2011). The ambient concentration of carbon monoxide (CO) was observed to be lower.

In conclusion, it was observed that sources of criteria pollutants in Lagos area are attributed to exhaust of vehicles (especially the old commercial vehicles and most cars in Nigeria are second hand cars popularly called Tokunboh) as well as the fumes emitted from the manufacturing factories which are evidently not kept in check. It was also observed that areas such as Oshodi, Ikeja, Iyana Ipaja, Ojota, and Ojodu Berger showed a high concentration level of ambient criteria pollutants. It was revealed in this study that ground level ozone, sulfur dioxide and nitrogen dioxide are the most important contributor to the occurrence of asthma, bronchitis and tuberculosis occurrence. The study also affirmed the relationship between criteria pollutants and the occurrence of asthma, bronchitis, heart failure, lung cancer and tuberculosis. Although the incidence and aggravation of these diseases cannot be directly attributed absolutely to these pollutants, deliberate regulatory and control measure by the state would do a lot more good than inaction.

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